

Scatterplot for: EXP00024 2021-02-15 (Experiment)

Report date: February 15, 2021 14:50

X-axis = ocimum control 3333

Y-axis = trreated 5

Corr coeff = 0.472953

Slope = 0.486308, Intercept = 2.984170

Spot count = 152

Norm units = Norm

